

3D'omics outreach video 2

Deliverable 2.8

Month 50 (October 2025)

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General project information

Title	Three-dimensional holo'omic landscapes to unveil host-microbiota interactions shaping animal production
Acronym	3D'omics
Grant Agreement No.	101000309
Funding Programme	Horizon 2020
Instrument	RIA (Research and Innovation Action)
Project start date	01/09/2021
Duration of the project	52 months

Project partners

#	Partner	Abbrev	Type	Country
1	University of Copenhagen	UCPH	University	Denmark
2	Center for Genomic Regulation	CRG	Research Center	Spain
3	Veterinary University of Vienna	UVM	University	Austria
4	Max Delbrück Center	MDC	Research Center	Germany
5	KU Leuven	KUL	University	Belgium
6	ETH Zurich	ETH	University	Switzerland
7	Ben Gurion University	BGU	University	Israel
8	Norwegian University of Life Sciences	NMBU	University	Norway
9	Afekta Technologies Limited	ATL	Industry, SME	Finland
10	Aviagen, Inc.	AVI	Industry	United Kingdom
11	Novogene Netherlands B.V.	NGE	Industry	The Netherlands
12	Biomin, GmbH	BIO	Industry	Austria
13	Norsvin SA	NOR	Industry	Norway
14	Center for Genomic Analysis	CNAG	Research Center	Spain

About this document

The original deliverable describing the 3D'omics videos consisted of two explainer videos and the deadline was month 24. Due to the two functions of the videos (project introduction and dissemination of results), their delivery was split into two parts in the first amendment. The first video (described in **Deliverable D2.3**) was about introducing the project and the technology we were planning to develop. This allowed for an early presentation of the project to the public and thus maximum diffusion. The second explainer video (described in this document) summarises the progress of the project and ensures the accessibility of the concept of the newly developed technology to various interested parties.

Video creation process

For the second explainer video (“3D'omics - Challenges and Solutions”), we again commissioned the subcontractor Madeclear ApS, based on our good experiences producing the first video. At a first meeting with Madeclear ApS on the 12th of March 2025, we proposed a draft video script describing the impact and outlook of 3D'omics. During this meeting, we realized it would instead be more beneficial to report on the challenges we faced during the development of the 3D'omics workflow and the solutions enabling us today to employ this methodology. The recordings for this video were done on the 2nd of May in the Madeclear studio (interview part) and on the 23rd of May in the laboratory of the Copenhagen University (methods part). Two rounds of feedback enabled us to give additional input on the video content.

Video concept

The second video is aimed at fellow researchers and showcases our work: How far we have come in the development of the 3D'omics method and what the future holds. It consists of studio interviews mixed with footage from the lab, and some animation to further support the main points. It is 5:18 minutes long, featuring 6 researchers who take turns telling the story.

Thumbnail of the Explainer Video: The 6 researchers from UCPH presenting their work in the 3D'omics pipeline, the hurdles they faced along the way, and how they overcame them.

The core of the storytelling is that each person had a goal, ran into a challenge, and then solved it in a unique/creative way.

Still images from the Explainer Video. From top left to bottom right: Indication of miniscule scale of the samples; manual labor required for sample preparation; issues with static electricity and the solution: ionising gun; issues with automatic sample preparation and the solution: painstaking optimisation processes; 3D'omics methods and the researchers behind the work.

The video's message: Four years ago, an international consortium called 3D'omics was formed to develop technology for studying microorganisms at the micron scale. We created an innovative workflow and have been working hard to turn this dream into reality. Our journey involved collecting tiny gut samples from animals, using laser-microscopy to cut micro-samples that were extremely small and difficult to handle due to static electricity (we solved this by using an ionizing gun). We then developed a new DNA retrieval method that skipped conventional extraction steps, enabling us to work with tiny amounts of DNA. Automating sample processing required reprogramming machinery for our unique sample sizes. After sequencing, we cross-validated our data using FISH. With these advances, we have developed and validated our method to study microbiomes also spatially. This breakthrough enables us now to address important biological questions about probiotics, pathogen resistance, sustainable diets, crop resilience, animal welfare, and human health by understanding microbial interactions at an unprecedented fine scale.

The final panel of the video shows the logos of all beneficiaries and acknowledges the funding through the European Commission.

Video location and dissemination

The video has been uploaded to the 3D'omics youtube channel on 11.06.2025 and can be watched via this link: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=RWeq0SPEJAM> It has also been linked to the 3D'omics website and shared on our social media channels.

The video has received over 220 views within the first 3 months of publication.

Video accessibility

The video contains sound (voice-over), as well as English subtitles. Automatic translation is enabled, so viewers can translate the subtitles into almost any language.

